

Digital Resilience Governance in India: Definitions, Measurement and Inclusion

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Summary

Climate change is disrupting ecosystems, economies, and societies at an accelerating rate, making the ability to define, measure and monitor resilience a central part of climate adaptation and disaster response. In highly climate-vulnerable countries like India, digital platforms have become central tools in efforts to manage climate adaptation and disaster risk mitigation - collecting data, producing indicators and visualising risks to support decision-making. This report analyses how India's national digital governance frameworks define and measure climate resilience, identifies patterns of inclusion and exclusion within these systems, and proposes concrete, inclusion-focused design and policy recommendations for resilience-tracking platforms. While governments often assume that digital tools will lead to better decision-making and more effective governance, these platforms are not neutral: they reflect governance structures, policy decisions and social inequalities. While governments increasingly rely on digital platforms to measure and monitor resilience, often assuming that these tools will lead to better decision-making and more effective governance, these platforms are not neutral: how resilience tracking is defined is shaped by governance structures, policy decisions, and social inequalities. A critical paradox emerges; digitisation does not automatically lead to inclusion and can instead reinforce existing inequalities when tools are designed without considering the needs and realities of marginalised communities. Addressing these gaps is urgent because resilience-tracking platforms are becoming infrastructural, shaping long-term access to adaptation resources without democratic oversight or community control. By drawing on critical infrastructure studies and digital-justice frameworks, the study aims to highlight opportunities for more human-centred, participatory resilience governance models. Key recommendations include bridging digital divides through infrastructure investment and literacy programmes, designing accessible multi-channel early-warning systems, ensuring that portals provide multi-language and accessibility features, and empowering communities through participatory governance and local data stewardship.

Introduction

Climate change is intensifying the frequency and severity of disasters, making digital resilience solutions a central goal of public policy. The IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report observes that most observed adaptation is fragmented, small in scale and sector-specific, designed to respond to current impacts and near-term risks (IPCC,2022). It warns, however, that adaptation gaps persist and calls for long-term planning and accelerated implementation (IPCC, 2022). Governments increasingly turn to digital platforms – for example, to satellite monitoring, predictive analytics and mobile-phone alerts – to monitor climate resilience, support decision making and inform citizens. Yet digital systems are not designed neutral: how resilience is defined and operationalized is embedded in governance structures, policy choices, and social inequalities. Studies have shown that technology-led resilience initiatives may reproduce patterns of exclusion if they are developed in centralized, technocratic spaces without democratic oversight (Oxfam India, 2022, Boyd & Crawford, 2012). Digitisation does not automatically lead to inclusion but rather, it can reinforce existing inequalities when tools are designed without considering the needs or realities of marginalised communities (Van Dijk, 2017.)

India is among the most climate vulnerable nations according to the Climate Risk Index 2025, which ranks the country sixth among nations most affected by extreme weather. The report notes that India experienced more than 400 extreme weather events between 1993 and 2022, causing nearly \$180 billion in losses and at least 80 000 fatalities (Germanwatch, 2025).

Yet in India, large digital divides persist: the ICUBE 2024 report estimates that there were 886 million active internet users in India in 2024, with rural India (488 million users) surpassing urban India (397 million users) but 41 % of the population still offline and more than half of rural residents not accessing the internet (IAMAI & Kantar, 2024). Oxfam's 2022 inequality report further notes that only about one-fifth of the population can operate a computer or use the internet, and that among the poorest 20 % of households, only 2.7 % own a computer and 8.9 % have internet access (Oxfam India, 2022). A diagnostic study highlights that India has invested in improved early-warning systems and emergency communications, including multi-hazard alerts and specialised centres of excellence (The Asia Foundation, 2022), For example, the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) has developed a Common Alerting Protocol

(CAP)-based Integrated Alert System and related tools such as the Sachet mobile application to deliver geo-targeted early warnings to citizens ¹. However gaps remain in inclusivity and reach.

This report examines how India's digital resilience governance frameworks define and measure resilience, identifies patterns of inclusion and exclusion, and proposes strategies to make digital resilience more equitable. It asks:

1. How do India's national digital frameworks for climate adaptation and disaster risk management define and operationalise resilience? What indicators, tools and data architectures are used?
2. What barriers prevent marginalised communities from accessing and benefitting from resilience-tracking tools? How do design decisions and governance arrangements embed social inequities?
3. How can human-centred design, participatory governance and data-justice principles be integrated into resilience platforms to ensure inclusivity?

To answer these questions, the report uses a qualitative document analysis, informed by three interlocking theoretical lenses: the digital divide, infrastructural exclusion and data justice. The analysis compares NDMA's initiatives with the global Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015–2030), which outlines four priorities -understanding risk, strengthening governance, investing in risk reduction and enhancing preparedness - and seven targets, including universal access to multi-hazard early warning systems (UNDRR, 2015).

2. Background / Literature review

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Sixth Assessment Report (AR6, 2023) underscores that measuring resilience is not just a technical issue, but it is also a governance decision that shapes access to climate adaptation resources. India, as the sixth most climate-vulnerable country in the world according to Climate risk index 2025, has implemented digital governance initiatives such as the Digital India Programme and the Smart Cities Mission to integrate data-driven sustainability planning into resilience strategies. These policies emphasize satellite monitoring, predictive analytics, and AI-powered risk assessments to

¹ <https://sachet.ndma.gov.in/>

improve adaptation planning. However, digitization does not automatically lead to inclusiveness as access, usage, and control over resilience data remain significant barriers. (Climate risk index 2025)

Digital Divide

Among the underlying concepts of digital divide literature is that digital divides reflect other patterns of socioeconomic inequality (Oxfam India, 2022). The existing research often focuses on the technological capabilities of resilience-tracking tools, but less attention is given to how governance frameworks shape digital accessibility and participation in decision-making. Therefore, the focus is to examine these two levels together. Van Dijk's digital divide framework (2020) highlights that digital inequalities exist at multiple levels and focuses on that just providing digital hardware or connectivity is not enough but rather meaningful inclusion requires skills, relevant content and supportive environments. It distinguishes between three levels: Firstly, the question of access - Who has the infrastructure and connectivity (*internet, mobile networks*) to use resilience tracking tools? Secondly, the skills and usage - Who has the skills and knowledge to engage with these tools effectively? (*digital literacy, motivation and cultural relevance*); Thirdly, the outcomes - who benefits from digital resources and digital resilience planning, and who is left out?

In India, digital divides mirror socio-economic structures: The ICUBE 2024 survey reports that there were 886 million active internet users in 2024, with rural users (488 million) outnumbering urban users (397 million), yet 41 % of the population remained offline and over half of rural residents were non-internet users (IAMAI & Kantar, 2024). Oxfam India's 2022 inequality report shows that In India, 70 per cent of the population has poor or no connectivity to digital services: in addition, only about one-fifth of the population can operate a computer or use the Internet and that among the poorest 20% of households, just 2,7% own a computer and 8,9 % have Internet access. On the contrary, among the top 20 per cent households the proportions are 27.6 per cent and 50.5 per cent. (Oxfam India, 2022). Moreover, gender, caste, and disabilities impact on access and use as well. The risk is that digital resilience tools that exclude marginalized communities from their design risk reproducing the very inequities they aim to solve.

This expanded model emphasises that digital inequality continues also after access is attained: scholars describe a "second-level" digital divide Van Dijk, 2017), where differences in skills,

usage and cultural appropriation of technology produce new forms of exclusion even long after physical access is achieved. Moreover, recent sociological research underscores that digital inequality is not just a technological problem but is also shaped by socio-economic conditions; a comparative study of rural and urban India found that the digital divide arises from persistent socio-economic divides and manifests across both settings, affecting access to digital education and economic opportunities (Laskar, 2023). These insights foreground the importance of examining digital divides when assessing resilience governance.

The Role of Design in Digital Resilience Tracking - Learning from Infrastructure Failures

Technology is often framed as an objective, neutral solution to governance challenges, but the way digital resilience-tracking platforms are designed has long-term consequences on inclusion and exclusion; Langdon Winner's bridge design example (1986) provides a clear analogy for this issue by demonstrating how seemingly neutral design decisions can embody social biases. Winner (1986) describes how low-hanging bridges on Long Island parkways in the United States were deliberately designed to prevent buses from passing underneath. This effectively meant that wealthier individuals with private cars could access certain areas, while poorer, often racialized communities who relied on public transportation were excluded. Once these bridges were built, exclusion was locked into the urban infrastructure, making it nearly impossible to undo. (Winner, 1986).

The same logic applies to digital resilience governance. Policy and practical initiatives often don't consider the causes nor the consequences of digital inequalities (Oxfam India, 2022). If digital resilience-tracking platforms are designed without considering digital literacy, access barriers, and governance structures, there is a risk that the exclusion becomes embedded into climate adaptation policies themselves (Van Dijk, 2017; UNDRR, 2023). The risk is that without intentional design, these systems may only serve the most digitally connected populations while leaving marginalized communities without meaningful access to resources (Boyd & Crawford, 2022; Milan & Trere, 2019). Interface design (colour schemes, language options, navigation), underlying data architectures and governance arrangements can structurally benefit certain users (urban, literate, smartphone-owners) while sidelining others (UNDRR, 2023). Analysing digital platforms as socio-technical infrastructures enables us to trace how exclusion is in a way built in through technology, policy and market forces (Boyd & Crawford, 2012; Milan & Trere, 2019).

Data justice and data-driven governance

Many resilience-tracking platforms rely on AI-driven risk assessment models, which are often presented as

unbiased and data-driven. In data justice research the main questions are who controls data, how datafication affects power relations and whether data practices actually empower or harm communities.

Cinnamon (2020) and Milan & Treré (2019) argue that data-driven governance often reinforces systemic inequalities rather than reducing them. Cinnamon (2020) also warns that development interventions often collect data from communities but rarely grant any control or benefits to the data subjects themselves. This approach risks extracting information without empowering those who need it (Cinnamon, 2020). Moreover, datasets used in AI risk assessment tools are shaped by historical power structures, meaning that resilience metrics may prioritize urban infrastructure while underrepresenting informal settlements and rural areas, where climate risks are often highest. (Cinnamon 2020; Milan&Trere, 2019) In the context of resilience tracking, this means that the communities most vulnerable to climate shocks may be the least able to engage with digital sustainability tools, leaving them out of adaptation planning entirely.

In India, The Digital India programme, launched in 2015, seeks to transform the country into a digitally empowered society and knowledge-based economy by ensuring digital access, inclusion and empowerment (Press Information Bureau, 2022a). However, there is a disconnect between what digital governance claims to do and what it enables in practice - while the policies often claim to improve inclusiveness and delve into other issues, the dilemma of whether it is actually enabled in practice remains. According to the Oxfam India 2022 report, the Digital India program has benefitted the privileged society more than the underprivileged. (Oxfam India, 2022). Moreover, gaps remain in inclusivity and reach and large digital divides persist. As these digital divides in inclusivity and reach remain which is why it is important to look into inclusion and exclusion matters in the case of digital resilience.

3. Methods

Research design

This study employs a qualitative document analysis of Indian policy documents and digital governance frameworks. Primary sources include the National Disaster Management Plan (NDMP 2019), NDMA guidelines and platform descriptions, and Digital India programme documents. These are compared against global frameworks such as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030 and UNDRR’s Inclusive Early Warning Early Action Checklist, as well as reports from the IPCC and the Asia Foundation. Secondary sources comprise government press releases, academic articles, NGO reports and media coverage.

The case example will investigate how India’s National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) measures and monitors resilience through digital systems, and how this aligns with the UN Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030. India is selected as a case study due to its high climate vulnerability, national-level disaster governance framework, and active use of digitisation in disaster risk management.

Analytical Framework and process

The analysis is guided by the theoretical lenses introduced in the literature review. Drawing on Van Dijk’s digital divide framework (2020), this study questions not only the access to digital platforms but also the capacity to use and benefit from them. Winner’s (1986) theory of infrastructural exclusion supports a design-sensitive reading of how digital platforms may embed inequalities. Cinnamon (2020) and Milan & Treré (2019) also provide a data justice lens, helping frame concerns around data ownership, control, and extractive governance practices. Inclusion/exclusion will be analysed using Van Dijk’s digital divide model, Milan & Treré’s infrastructural exclusion, and Cinnamon’s data justice framework, applied to each mapped indicator/tool.

The analytical process follows four iterative steps. First, relevant Sendai targets and indicators that involve measurement, monitoring and reporting of resilience were identified. Second, NDMA resilience indicators and associated digital tools and platforms were extracted from

national documents. Third, NDMA indicators and tools were compared against Sendai targets to visualise alignments, partial alignments and gaps. Finally, the inclusiveness of each indicator or tool was evaluated using the digital-divide, infrastructural-exclusion and data-justice lenses. Coding was guided by categories such as definitions of resilience; measurement metrics and data sources; monitoring and visualisation practices; signals of inclusion and exclusion (language, access, skills, participation mechanisms); and data governance (control and ownership). The iterative coding enabled the analysis to capture both explicit policy narratives and implicit assumptions embedded in platform design and governance structures.

1. How do India's national digital frameworks define and operationalise resilience? What indicators, tools and data architectures are used?
2. Inclusion and exclusion: What barriers prevent marginalised communities from accessing and benefitting from resilience-tracking tools? How do design decisions and governance arrangements embed social inequities?
3. Critical perspective: How do human-centred design, participatory governance and data-justice principles challenge or reproduce existing inequities when applied to resilience platforms? These questions asked link the methodological steps to the broader theoretical concerns and set the stage for the results and discussion

4. Results / analysis

4.1 Defining and measuring resilience

Indian policy documents define resilience primarily through risk indicators and early warning systems. NDMA's National Disaster Management Plan 2019 articulates resilience as the capacity to prepare for, withstand as well as recover from disaster. In addition, the operationalisation ventures on monitoring hazards, forecasting impacts and distributing alerts. Digital tools, such as the Dynamic Composite Risk Atlas & Decision Support System and Flood Hazard Atlas gather together hazard data such as cyclone tracks, floodplains and vulnerability indices, into a geospatial online platform. The Common Alerting Protocol (CAP)-based Integrated Alert Systems uses various different communication channels, such as SMS, television, radio, cell and broadcasts in order to deliver geo-targeted warnings. It also includes the Sachet mobile application that supports multiple Indian languages.

NDMA also operates a National Disaster Alert Portal, which is branded as Sached, as well as the India Disaster Resource Network (IDRN), which collects together official warnings, preparedness information and other resources in English. (NDMA, 2025b). These platforms prioritise hazard-centric metrics such as flood levels, cyclone paths, warning lead times, while largely omitting social vulnerability indicators such as income, housing type or disability status. It seems that Digital resilience is thus defined in technocratic terms: resilience equals timely hazard detection and dissemination.

India's early-warning architecture is multi-agency and the taking closer look into them reveals there are various digital resilience initiatives; The India Meteorological Department (IMD) operates hundreds of surface observatories, radio and balloon stations and collaborates with national and international partners to issue alerts on cyclones, floods, rainfall and earthquakes (The Asia Foundation, 2022). The Indian National Centre for Oceanic Information Services (INCOIS) hosts the country's tsunami warning system, issuing bulletins within an hour of seismic events and running regular simulation exercises (The Asia Foundation, 2022). The Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) provides satellite-based communication networks, hazard databases and geospatial analysis through the National Remote Sensing Centre (The Asia Foundation, 2022). Also, Academic institutions such as the Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee have developed earthquake early-warning sensors and mobile applications for Uttarakhand, giving residents seconds to react (The Asia Foundation, 2022). These institutional collaborations showcase how digital resilience is operationalised through technical expertise and data infrastructures, however social vulnerability metrics remain largely absent.

Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 UNDRR

The Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction is the UN's global agreement that runs from 2015 to 2030. It was adopted by all UN Member States as a shared commitment to reduce disaster risks, prevent losses in lives and assets, and build stronger resilience. The aim is to achieve *'substantial reduction of disaster risk and losses in lives, livelihoods and health and in the economic, physical, social, cultural and environmental assets of persons, businesses, communities and countries over the next 15 years.'* The Framework sets out seven global targets and four priorities for action: understanding risk, strengthening governance, investing in risk reduction, and enhancing preparedness - including the principle of *"Build Back Better"* after disasters. Importantly, Sendai emphasizes a multi-hazard, all-of-society approach, where

governments, local authorities, communities, and even the private sector share responsibility. (UNDRR, 2015).

In this research, the Sendai Framework serves as a global benchmark for resilience measurement, outlining targets and indicators against which national efforts can be assessed. India's National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) has developed an array of digital systems ranging from disaster databases and early-warning applications to satellite-monitoring platforms to track and manage resilience. By comparing NDMA's tools with the Sendai indicators, the research evaluates how closely these national systems align with international expectations and identifies where gaps persist. Although Sendai does not explicitly mandate the creation of apps or dashboards, it implicitly assumes digitisation: understanding risk depends on data collection and analysis; strengthening governance relies on robust information flows; investing in resilience increasingly involves building digital infrastructure; and enhancing preparedness often draws on digital early-warning mechanisms. This implicit reliance on digital tools is central to my inquiry. Sendai defines what should be measured, while NDMA's platforms demonstrate how such measurements are operationalised. However, digitisation is not neutral; its design choices may amplify exclusion by privileging certain communities and rendering others invisible. Thus, the Sendai Framework functions both as a reference point for resilience measurement and as a lens through which to interrogate whether NDMA's digital innovations promote inclusive resilience or entrench new forms of inequality.

Comparing NDMA's initiatives with the Sendai Framework reveals both convergence and gaps. Sendai Target G calls for increased availability of multi-hazard early warning systems; NDMA's CAP-based alert system and the Sachet app directly advance this target by providing geo-targeted warnings in multiple languages. Sendai's emphasis on understanding risk (Priority 1) resonates with NDMA's hazard atlases and risk maps. However, Sendai also highlights strengthening disaster-risk governance, investing in social resilience and enhancing preparedness through community participation—areas where national policies are weaker. NDMA's metrics are predominantly quantitative and hazard-centric, aligning with Sendai's measurable indicators but neglecting qualitative aspects of resilience such as social capital, local knowledge and equity. However, while Sendai stresses inclusive, disaggregated data and participation of vulnerable groups, NDMA's digital platforms lack provisions for co-design or community data ownership, underscoring a gap between global aspirations and national practice.

However, one needs to remember that one system can't do it all and it is good to remember that India has many frameworks and tools.

Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 targets			
Priority 1	Priority 2	Priority 3	Priority 4
Understanding disaster risk	Strengthening disaster risk governance to manage disaster risk	Investing in disaster reduction for resilience	Enhancing disaster preparedness for effective response

Source: UN Sendai Framework 2015-2030 (UNISDR)

4.3. Inclusion and exclusion patterns

Applying the digital-divide, infrastructural-exclusion and data-justice lenses uncovers significant barriers to inclusion. First, access divides persist: ICUBE report reveals how 41 per cent of the population remains offline and more than half of rural residents are non-interent users (IAMAI & Kantar, 2024). Among the poorest households, only 2,7 per cent own a computer and 8,9 per cent have internet access (Oxfam India, 2022) Requiring smartphones, data plans and stable connectivity to receive warnings privileges urban, literate populations and excludes many in rural, remote or low-income communities. However, the access is not the only case to look at as skills and usage divides further limit participation: digital literacy, motivation and cultural relevance influence whether people can interpret alerts and use dashboards; the portals mostly are only in a few languages include many, and even when that is the case language or accessibility features may not accommodate those with disabilities or low literacy skills. In addition, outcome divides arise when even those who receive alters lack the resources - safe housing, savings, mobility for example – to respond.

Secondly, infrastructural exclusion is embedded in platform design and architecture. While the Sachet app and NDMA dashboards are available in several languages, they only cover the major languages including many in a country of hundreds of languages. Key portals such as the India Disaster Resource Network are English-only and their websites are often inaccessible from

low-bandwidth connections which I also happened to experience during doing this research in a low-connectivity area: High-resolution maps and complex interfaces assume high-speed internet and modern devices. These design choices reproduce socio-spatial inequalities, much like Winner's low bridges that kept buses away from affluent suburbs. Additionally, the architecture of data flows such as centralised servers, proprietary algorithms and opaque risk models do further exclude users from understanding or influencing the systems that govern them.

Third, data-justice concerns permeate digital resilience. Data collected through NDMA's platforms is controlled by government agencies, with little transparency about how it is collected, used or shared. Communities rarely seem to own or govern the digital data they generate; instead, resilience metrics feed back into centralized decision-making. Without clear governance frameworks and community participation, digital resilience initiatives risk becoming tools of surveillance and control rather than empowerment. The result is therefore a paradox: digital platforms intended to democratise resilience can entrench existing hierarchies if power asymmetries in access, design and data ownership remain unchallenged.

5. Discussion

India's digital resilience governance demonstrates both remarkable progress but also deep inequalities. Multi-hazard alert systems, satellite-based monitoring and earthquake early-warning apps show how investment and technical collaboration have expanded hazard coverage (The Asia Foundation, 2022). However, there is a disconnect between what digital governance frameworks promise and what they enable in practice. While policy documents often claim to improve inclusiveness and address the needs of vulnerable groups, in real life, digital systems often are inaccessible to those without reliable connectivity or knowledge how to use them or how to look for them. In addition, national portals can be slow or unreachable pointing to a gap between intent and implementation. Moreover, climate adaptation planning in India is devolved to the states, each of which develops its own climate action plan; this results in uneven integration of digital resilience strategies and highlights the need for national coordination and support. These innovations therefore operate within a society marked by stark digital divides and socio-economic disparities, meaning that technological solutions alone cannot deliver equitable resilience. The case echoes Winner's notion that infrastructures embed social choices: by assuming smartphone ownership and online literacy, NDMA's platforms privilege urban, educated users and exclude those most vulnerable.

Comparative analysis with the Sendai Framework reveals a hazard-centric approach that prioritises monitoring and alerting but pays less attention to community empowerment, data sharing and social resilience. Despite Big Data narratives' myths of objectivity and universalism (Boyd & Crawford, 2012), resilience governance relies on data as a proxy for resilience, forgetting the social contexts that make data meaningful. In addition, gendered and caste-based norms shape access to mobile phones, freedom of movement and trust in state communication. Persons with disabilities face physical and sensory barriers to receiving warnings. Without acknowledging these intersecting dimensions, digital resilience initiatives risk reinforcing existing hierarchies. Digital governance policies present resilience tracking as a neutral, technical solution, yet these policies are often developed in centralized decision-making spaces with limited input from affected communities. While digital tools are intended to make resilience measurement more effective, the assumption that data alone can drive better policy overlooks the structural inequalities that influence who has the ability to use and benefit from digital resilience tracking frameworks.

Finally, the governance of data itself is pivotal. Without transparent algorithms, community data stewardship and rights-based frameworks, early-warning systems may drift towards surveillance and control. Local data repositories, community-owned hazard maps and citizen science initiatives offer alternative models where data flows both upward to inform policy and back downward to empower adaptation strategies. Shifts in the development funding environment have also weakened community-based adaptation programmes: many non-governmental organisations that once supported disaster preparedness have faced funding cuts and regulatory pressures, reducing their capacity to help rural communities engage with digital tools. As a result, resilience governance risks becoming increasingly centralised and technocratic unless participatory mechanisms and sustained financial support are prioritised.

Conclusion

The aim of this study has been to get insights on how resilience is defined, measured, and governed in these digital systems by analysing how issues like digital access, design choices, and data ownership impact who actually benefits, and who gets left behind. However, these digital governance frameworks might unintentionally reproduce inequalities, much like poorly designed physical infrastructure can. Ultimately, it is important to emphasize how we can embed

human-centred design and local data control into these systems, so they're more inclusive, just, and actually usable by the communities most affected by climate change.

This study has underscored that technological solutions alone cannot overcome structural inequalities: Universal design and digital literacy programmes may improve usability, a critical social scientific perspective demands deeper questions – who designs these systems, who actually benefits from them and whose knowledge counts, whose does not? Digital platforms are often framed as neutral fixes, yet they can widen the digital divide by assuming smartphone ownership, literacy or connectivity. Also, efforts to expand internet infrastructure and provide multilingual interfaces are necessary but at this stage, insufficient. They must be designed with the intention and redistributive policies addressing poverty, patriarchy, caste, as well as disability discrimination.

Similarly, calls for participatory governance should not mask power imbalances. Co-design processes frequently involve symbolic consultation rather than genuine community engagement. Localized data stewardship models offer an alternative approach, where communities retain control over their climate and risk-related data. These models ensure that resilience tracking is not only inclusive but also actionable for those directly affected by climate change. When communities own their data, they can integrate it into locally meaningful adaptation strategies, ensuring that resilience frameworks reflect lived experiences rather than imposed metrics. Local data governance also strengthens climate adaptation and risk mitigation, as community-led insights can shape policy solutions that respond to the specific vulnerabilities of informal settlements and rural areas. Data-justice principles often emphasise that communities should own and govern the data they generate; however, current frameworks rarely challenge state and corporate control. Algorithmic transparency is indeed important, however transparency in itself does not solve the political choices embedded in risk models. Therefore, scholars must question the very assumptions behind risk quantification and ask whose resilience is actually being measured.

Critical engagement with global frameworks, such as the Sendai Framework examined in this report, reveals a tension between universal indicators and local realities. While Sendai recommends multi-hazard early warning systems and inclusive policies, its metrics may privilege measurable infrastructure over social cohesion and lived experience. Researchers and practitioners should examine how global agendas are translated into national plans and how they

may risk marginalising indigenous knowledge or alternative epistemologies. Future work should therefore focus on power dynamics in digital resilience governance, exploring how data practices can be decolonized and how communities can assert sovereignty over their information and adaptation strategies.

Digitisation offers powerful tools to monitor hazards and disseminate warnings, but digital resilience is not automatically inclusive. India's experience shows that even sophisticated multi-hazard systems can leave behind those who lack connectivity, literacy or social power. By integrating nuanced understandings of the digital divide, scrutinizing infrastructural design, and implementing data-justice principles, policymakers can transform digital platforms from instruments of technocratic control into tools for resilience. Future research should explore community-led pilot projects, empirically assess how inclusive design affects outcomes, and examine the political economies that shape digital governance in disaster contexts. Ultimately, true resilience is built not only through data and technology but through participation, equity, and collective agency in order to make sure the ones who are easily excluded would be included.

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